

Development of Derivatives Markets in India

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Introduction

With the end of the system of administered prices and centrally allocated resources a new global economic order emerged. The Bretton Woods system of fixed exchange rates came under stress in the 1970s, and this led to freeing exchange rates, opening up the economy and varying prices according to the market conditions. Price fluctuations in open economies make it hard for businesses to estimate their future production costs and revenue. Derivatives securities provide them with a valuable set of tools for managing this risk. Hence, the present paper aims to study the development of derivatives markets in India.

Derivatives

A derivative is a financial instrument whose value depends on that of other variables/assets called the underlying asset, which could be commodity, security, interest rate, share price index and so on. They do not constitute ownership; rather they are a promise to convey ownership.

Forward Contract

A forward contract is a one-to-one contract which is to be performed in future on the terms decided today. Forward contracts are being used in India on a large scale in the foreign exchange market to cover the currency risk.

They are negotiated by parties on a one-to-one basis and offer tremendous flexibility to them to articulate a contract in terms of price, quantity, quality, delivery time and place. However, they suffer from poor liquidity and default risk.

Future Contract

Future contracts are organized or standardized in terms of quantity, quality, delivery and place for settlement on any date in future. These contracts are traded on exchanges.

In future markets are the extension of forward contracts. They are being organized or standardized and are very liquid by their own nature.

Option

Option is a contract which gives the buyer (holder) the right, but not the obligation, to buy or sell a specified quantity of the underlying assets, at a specific price by a specified time. They may be physical commodities like wheat, rice, cotton, gold, oil etc. or financial instruments like equity stock, stock index, bonds etc.

Scope of the Study

This paper describes the development, structure and regulation of Indian derivative markets.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the origin and development of derivatives market in India.
2. To know the structure of derivatives market in India.
3. To analyse the benefits of derivatives market in India.
4. To study the categories of derivatives traded in India.
5. To analyse the derivatives regulations in the Indian stock market.
6. To find out the regulatory instruments used in the derivatives market in India.

Origin of Derivatives Market in India

Derivatives markets have been in existence in India in some form or other for a long time. In the area of commodities, the Bombay Cotton Trade Association started futures trading in 1875, and by the early 1900s India had one of the world's largest futures industries. In 1952, the Government banned cash settlement and options trading and derivatives trading shifted to informal forwards markets. In the recent years, the Government policy has changed, allowing for an increased role for market based pricing and less suspicion of derivatives trading. The ban on futures trading of many commodities started being lifted in the early 2000s, and national electronic commodity exchanges were created.

Development of Derivatives Market in India

The economic liberalization of the early nineties facilitated the introduction of derivatives based on interest rates and foreign exchange. The easing of various restrictions on the free movement of interest rates resulted in the need to manage interest rate risk. The sequence of events leading to the introduction and trading of derivatives is present in the following table.

Table 1 Development of Derivatives Market in India

Sl. No.	Date	Derivatives Market in India
1	14 December 1995	NSE asked SEBI for permission to trade index futures
2	18 November 1996	Formed L.C.Gupta Committee to design a policy framework for index futures
3	7 July 1999	RBI gave permission for OTC forward rate agreements (FRAs) and interest rate swaps
4	24 May 2000	SIMEX chose Nifty for trading futures and options on an Indian index
5	25 May 2000	SEBI gave permission to NSE and BSE to do index futures trading
6	9 June 2000	Trading of BSE Sensex futures commenced at BSE
7	12 June 2000	Trading of NIFTY futures commenced at NSE
8	25 September 2000	Nifty futures trading commenced at SGX
9	June 2001	Index options introduced

10	July 2001	Stock options introduced
11	November 2001	Stock futures
12	June 2003	Trading on interest rate futures commenced at NSE
13	July 2003	Trading on FC-rupee options started
14	June 2007	Trading on Nifty Junior Options and Futures started

Participants of Derivatives Market in India

1. Hedgers use futures or options markets to reduce or eliminate the risk associated with the price of an asset.
2. Speculators use futures and option contracts to get an extra leverage in betting on future movements in the price of the asset. They can increase both the potentials gains and potential losses by using derivatives in a speculative venture.
3. Arbitrageurs are in business to take advantage of the discrepancy between prices in two different markets.

Structure of Derivatives Market in India

The structure of Indian derivatives markets can be illustrated with the help of the following chart.

Benefits of Derivatives Market in India

The benefits of derivatives market in India are as follows:

1. India's financial market system will strongly benefit from smoothly functioning index derivatives markets.
2. Internationally, the launch of derivatives has been associated with substantial improvements in market quality on the underlying equity market. Liquidity and market efficiency on India's equity market will improve.
3. Many risks can be eliminated by diversification in the financial markets. Index derivatives are special in so far as they can be used by investors to protect themselves from the one risk in the equity market that cannot be diversified away i.e. a fall in the market index.
4. Foreign investors coming into India will be more comfortable if the hedging vehicles routinely used by them worldwide are available to them.
5. The launch of derivatives is a logical next step in the development of human capital in India. Skills have grown tremendously in the financial sector in the last few years.

Categories of Derivatives Traded in India

The various categories of derivatives traded in India are as follows:

1. Commodities futures for coffee, oil seeds, oil, gold, silver, pepper, cotton, jute and jute goods are traded in the commodities futures. The forward markets commission regulates the trading of commodities futures.
2. Index futures based on Sensex, NIFTY index, Nifty junior, CNX IT and Bank Nifty are also traded under the supervision of SEBI.
3. The RBI has permitted banks, financial institutions (FIs) and primary dealers (PDs) to enter into forward rate agreements (FRAs), interest rate swaps in order to facilitate the hedging of interest rate risk and ensure orderly development of the derivatives market.
4. The National Stock Exchange became the first exchange to launch trading in options on individual securities. Options contracts are American style and cash-settled and are available in about 188 securities stipulated by SEBI.
5. NSE commenced trading in futures on individual securities on November 9, 2001. The futures contracts are available in about 188 securities stipulated by SEBI. BSE also started trading in the stock options and futures (both index and stocks) at around the same time as NSE.
6. NSE commenced trading in interest rate futures on June 2003. Interest rate futures contracts are available on 91 day T bills, 10 year bonds and 10 year zero coupon bonds as specified by SEBI.

Table 2 Derivatives Products Introduced in Indian Financial Markets

Sl. No	OTC	Exchange Traded
1	1980s – Currency forwards	June 2000 – Equity index futures
2	1997 – Long term foreign currency – rupee swaps	June 2001 – Equity index options
3	July 1999 – Interest rate swaps and FRAs	July 2001 – Stock option
4	July 2003 – FC – Rupee options	June 2003 – Interest rate futures
5		June 2007 – Futures and options on Nifty junior

Derivatives Regulations in the Indian Stock Market

The Indian trading system comprises the exchange at the top-which is governed by the three governing bodies:

1. Governing Council
2. Governing Board
3. Clearing Member.

It is further assisted by clearing house, clearing bank, clearing member, trading member and the client, and the trade guarantee fund and the investor protection fund are part of the risk reduction scheme. Structurally, the exchange performs several functions like order matching, clearance and settlement, risk management including default management and investor protection.

Regulatory Instruments used in Derivatives Market in India

Margin Variation

A margin is a proportion of the derivative contract value which has to be paid in cash or securities by the seller or the buyer or both, as the case may be in the future market. The regulatory authorities frequently use this instrument to check the high speculation and thinness of the market.

Imposition of Special Margins

Special margins refer to those margins which are imposed by the regulatory authorities over and above the ordinary margins.

Daily or Weekly Limits on Price Changes

The basic objective of this tool is to keep the prices of futures instruments in a particular band or limits.

Limits on the Open Position

The term open position relates to the limit on the volume of trading for a particular instrument for the traders in the market.

Temporary Suspension of Trading

According to this measure, the regulatory authority stops the trading in a particular asset temporarily for a particular period.

Changes in the Number and/ or Timing of Contracts

The measure is related to the change in the number and timing of the futures contract being traded because sometimes it is not well suited to the seasonality of supply and demand of a particular asset or commodity.

Fixation of Price Limits

In this technique the regulatory authority fixes the price limits, i.e. the maximum and/or minimum which the futures market is not allowed to move out. The basis idea is to protect the markets at the time of shortages or gluts.

Conclusion

To prepare the Indian economy to be able to bear more risk, the need for derivatives cannot be overlooked. Financial derivatives are considered for inclusion is the risk control arsenal of organization. They allow an efficient transfer of financial risks and can help to ensure that value enhancing opportunities are not ignored. When used properly they can reduce risk and increase returns. Thus, they should be integrated into an organisation's risk management strategy and be in harmony with its broader corporate philosophy and objectives. There is no fear from derivatives if they are used properly with requisite expertise.

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